

Beyond Static and Dynamic Quantization - Hybrid Quantization of Vision Transformers

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Abstract

Vision Transformers excel in computer vision. However, deploying these models on edge devices is challenging due to their high memory and computational requirements. Furthermore, they suffer from outliers in the activation maps at inference. Dynamic quantization generally attains the best accuracy but adds quantization and dequantization overhead. While static quantization reduces model latency, it usually degrades accuracy. We propose a hybrid quantization technique that selects a linear layer for either static or dynamic quantization based on the signal-to-noise ratio using a floating-point model as a reference. Our method attains reduced latency and memory usage of static quantization while improving model accuracy with minimal compute overhead. For DeiT3-S/16/224, DeiT3-B/16/384, and DeiT3-L/16/224, we improve top-1 accuracy by up to 1%, 4%, and 11.5%, respectively, over static INT8 quantization. At the same time, we reach an average speedup of 1.87, 1.88, and 1.69 over dynamic INT8 quantization on the ImageNet1K dataset.

1 Introduction

Vision transformers (ViTs) are a new family of models used in computer vision (CV) for tasks such as image classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, and image generation [10, 18, 20, 62, 69] adapted from natural language processing transformers [37]. ViTs are particularly useful in scenarios where large amounts of visual data are available. They outperform traditional convolutional neural networks in specific tasks [13], making them an exciting area of research and development in CV. Unfortunately, the performance of ViTs comes at the cost of memory and computational complexity. Concretely, ViTs come in various sizes, starting from 5.7 million and going up to 22 billion parameters. [8]. In addition, ViTs differ in training methods, attention layers, or additional operations [23, 28, 34, 35, 65]. Furthermore, researchers have shown that the ViTs tend to produce outliers attributed to background [9, 6]. These features make ViTs ideal but difficult candidates for compression.

Quantization is an approximation technique that reduces the number of bits used for storage and computation in deep learning models [15, 25, 27]. For example, it can reduce the bit width from 32 to 8 bits, saving up to 75% required memory. In addition, we can convert the data type from floating point (FP) to integer using a linear transformation. As a result, we can use more energy-efficient arithmetic units [6, 56]. However, this reduced precision in representing model parameters and activations can cause quantization errors, leading to degraded accuracy.

There exist two main post-training quantization methods: static and dynamic. Static quantization requires a calibration dataset to compute quantization parameters, which are set once for the lifetime of the quantized model. This method achieves lower latency, but often at the cost of reduced model precision. On the contrary, dynamic quantization computes quantization parameters on the fly, during inference, for selected supported layers. While it adds quantization overhead, it keeps the model accuracy closer to the reference [12]. Given the target hardware and the model, we need to consider the applied quantization type depending on the device’s capabilities. Static quantization is preferred in compute and memory-constrained environments, while dynamic quantization is preferred only in memory-bound environments. Deep learning algorithms in modern smartphones are memory-bound, yet have powerful processors and dedicated tensor processing units. [9, 7, 19].

Given the new ViTs architecture, we investigate whether it would be possible to combine static and dynamic quantization within this family of models. As a result, we expect to take the best of both methods: decreased latency compared to dynamic and improved performance compared to static quantization. For this purpose, we propose a hybrid quantization (HQ) approach where the selected layers are dynamically quantized while the rest of the model is statically quantized. More concretely, we present a novel hybrid quantization algorithm with automatic selection criteria based on the signal-to-quantization-noise ratio metric for dynamic or static quantized linear layers. Our contributions are as follows:

- We propose a novel hybrid quantization algorithm that combines static and dynamic quantization within a family of ViT models. We show that the performance of DeiT3 [55] improves by 1%, 4%, and 11.5% for small, base, and large on the ImageNet1K validation dataset [9]. Our method improves performance over statically quantized models in 12/12 ViT, 3/6 DeiT [55], 6/6 DeiT3, and 6/6 Swin Transformer [23].
- We measure the latency on the iPhone 13 Pro with an A15 Bionic CPU. Compared to dynamic quantization, for ViT family models we report an average speedup latency at 1.23 and 1.28 for HQ1 and HQ3 on the A15 Bionic CPU. Similarly, for DeiT3 family models, we achieve an average speedup of 1.33 and 1.29 for HQ1 and HQ3 on the same CPU.
- Likewise, we measure latency on a workstation equipped with an NVIDIA A100 GPU. Compared to dynamic quantization, we achieve an average speedup of 1.68 for ViT models, 1.72 for DeiT3 models for HQ1, and 1.69 for HQ3.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: first, in Section 2, we review related work on the quantization of ViTs. Next, in Section 3, we describe the methodology, and define quantization, static quantization, and dynamic quantization. Then we introduce hybrid quantization and describe all its variants. In Section 4, we introduce our experimental setup followed by analysis of the static quantization, dynamic quantization, FQ-ViT, and HQ in Section 5. We discuss the results and limitations of our study in Section 6. Finally, we conclude our work in Section 7.

2 Related work

Compression of deep learning models, especially foundation models [2], aims to reduce their size and complexity without significantly sacrificing accuracy. An alternative to quantization is pruning, which removes the unnecessary weights from the model. This involves setting weights and activations to 0 (with specific memory format representation) to reduce memory consumption. However, Kuzmin *et al.* [17] showed that quantization without fine-tuning is in most cases more accurate than unstructured pruning for vision models, including ViTs.

In the literature, hybrid quantization is an overloaded term. Nazari and Salehi used hybrid quantization to mix fixed-point and power-of-two quantization to compress ResNet-18 and deploy it on FPGA [24]. Panda proposed a hybrid quantization method - QUANOS, which assigns different bit width precision to convolutional layers [29]. This method explored the details of quantization in the context of adversarial robustness. Pandey *et al.* applied a mixed-precision iterative algorithm that, based on the signal-to-quantization-noise ratio metric, assigned the smallest bit width that did not degrade the model’s accuracy [60]. They showed that their method integrates with AdaRound [24] and that mixed-precision could outperform static quantization.

Lastly, there is ongoing research to enable integer-only inference of deep learning models. That enables running ViTs on devices without FP arithmetic units. I-ViT converted SoftMax, GeLU, and LayerNorm to ShiftMax, ShiftGeLU, and I-LayerNorm, respectively, using bit-shifting instead of multiplication [21]. Similarly, FQ-ViT approximated only SoftMax and LayerNorm [6] in integer arithmetic, omitting the GeLU [14] activation function [22].

While there is active research on ViT quantization, most studies focus on static quantization with mixed precision. Moreover, they introduce approximations to the activation functions and layer normalizations that require custom kernel implementations for each platform. We are the first to propose a hybrid approach mixing static with dynamic quantization in ViT.

3 Methodology

This study investigates post-training hybrid quantization for vision transformers to improve efficiency while maintaining accuracy. We present a novel algorithm that dynamically selects between static and dynamic quantization based on the signal-to-noise ratio. In Section 3.2, we discuss the design of the hybrid quantization algorithm.

3.1 Quantization

Quantization is an approximation method that addresses the problem of representing a large set of values in a compressed format. The idea behind quantization is to map a range of continuous input values to a smaller set of discrete output values. This is commonly used in digital signal processing as well as in image and video processing. While quantization can result in a certain loss of information, this is usually an acceptable trade-off for the benefits it provides in terms of storage and processing efficiency. In deep learning, the weights and activations of the model are represented in 32-bit FP precision. With quantization, we can reduce the number of bits and the data type, *e.g.*, to an 8-bit integer (INT8) or an 8-bit unsigned integer (UINT8). To convert a tensor X of weights or activations from FP32 to INT8/UINT8, we need to determine its scale s . One of the base functions is to calculate the

absolute maximum over the tensor divided by the data type representation

$$s = \frac{\max(|(X)|)}{\frac{q_{max}-q_{min}}{2}}, \quad (1)$$

where q_{min} and q_{max} are the upper and lower bounds of the quantized data type: INT8 (-128 and +127, respectively) and UINT8 (0 and +255, respectively). The quantization function

$$Q(X) = \left\lfloor \frac{X}{s} \right\rfloor + z_p, \quad (2)$$

then applies an element-wise scale transformation to the tensor X and rounds the result to the nearest integer. The quantization can be symmetric or asymmetric, depending on whether the zero point offset, z_p , is zero or not. We can dequantize the output by multiplying the integer shifted tensor $Q(X)$ by its scale s to recover an approximation of the original FP value:

$$DQ(Q(X)) = (Q(X) - z_p) \cdot s. \quad (3)$$

Static Quantization. Performing static quantization Q^S requires calibrating the model with a representative data set. This set of calibration samples determines the estimated range of values for the model activations. Using this information, we can reduce the loss of precision during the quantization process. Nevertheless, the usual calibration set consists of a few samples. As a result, it can not capture the model activations’ full dynamic range. Therefore, the intermediate activations may be clipped. Calibration is a process that records statistics of the activations for each node in the model graph, both at the input and output of the node. This allows us to compute the scale factor s for each layer and quantize all layers in the model graph, including normalization layers, parameterized layers (such as convolutional and linear layers), and activations. During inference, once the input is quantized, we can process the data using integer arithmetic only.

Dynamic quantization. Dynamic quantization Q^D is a technique that can be applied to linear layers without requiring a calibration set. This is useful for models that suffer significant precision drops when subject to static quantization. This method involves converting the weights of the linear layer to INT8, which reduces the model’s memory consumption. However, for each layer, its input is dynamically quantized, meaning that we must determine the scale factor s , convert the inputs from FP32 to INT8/UINT8, and then dequantize them back to FP32 at the output. This increases the computational overhead. Consequently, the remaining computations in the deep neural network are also performed in FP32.

3.2 Hybrid quantization

Consider a deep neural network ViT as a directed acyclic graph that processes the input I sequentially through m nodes $\mathcal{N} \in \mathcal{N}_1, \mathcal{N}_2, \dots, \mathcal{N}_m$ and outputs a tensor Y . Each node \mathcal{N} is a single operation in ViT, *e.g.*, matrix multiplication, GELU activation [14], LayerNorm [15], and so on. We want to statically quantize nodes such as normalization layers, activation functions, and attention modules. However, the linear layers can be statically or dynamically quantized. We expect that linear layers susceptible to quantization will be dynamically quantized while robust ones will be statically quantized. Similar to dynamic quantization, skip connections have to be left in FP arithmetic to allow the signal to go through the network. As a result, the majority of the operations will be executed using quantized arithmetic. We

Figure 1: A high-level overview of HQ* Algorithms. During the tuning phase, the SQNR is calculated between outputs of the same linear node (N) between the models. The produced model consists of a mixture of static or dynamic quantized blocks used for the inference.

have designed our hybrid quantization algorithm based on the signal-to-quantization-noise ratio (SQNR)

$$SQNR(X, Q(X)) = 20 \log_{10} \frac{P_S}{P_N} = 20 \log_{10} \frac{\|X\|}{\|X - Q(X)\|} [dB], \quad (4)$$

where P_S and P_N respectively represent the power of the signal and the power of the quantization noise. This metric measures the signal quality between the quantized and the baseline deep neural network. A higher SQNR value represents better signal quality, meaning the quantization error is less pronounced, and the quantized model is closer to its full-precision baseline. We used the Frobenius norm to calculate the maximum signal amplitude and the difference between the original and quantized signals. To select the appropriate quantization method, either static or dynamic, we compared the computed SQNR and select the quantization method with a stronger signal. We have developed three different methods based on the measuring SQNR signal: Hybrid Quantization 1 (HQ1) measures the signal passing through the quantized network against the baseline signal at the linear layer. We have to dequantize the intermediate activations before passing them to the reference model. HQ2 passes both the quantized and original signals through their respective networks independently. Finally, HQ3 quantizes the signal from a baseline deep neural network and then passes it through a quantized neural network. Figure 1 presents a high-level overview of the methods and the flows of the signal through the networks, as well as a simplified model overview used for inference. The implementation details are presented in the Algorithm 1 provided in supplementary materials. On the one hand, in HQ1, we measure how the quantized output affects the signal of the baseline model. On the other hand, with HQ3, we pass the signal from the baseline model to the quantized one. As a result, we measure how quantization influences the signal in the quantized model. Lastly, HQ2 allows us to estimate how processing through the networks independently affects the signal between quantized and baseline models.

4 Experimental setup

This section details our experimental setup, including the models and datasets employed. We report the top-1 accuracy achieved on the ImageNet1k dataset and the latency of the

proposed hybrid quantization method when executed on both an Apple A15 Bionic CPU and an NVIDIA A100 80GB GPU. We analyze our results, comparing them to those obtained from other quantization methods. For our research, we used pre-trained ViTs obtained from the timm package [68]. We considered four types of transformers: Vision Transformers (ViT) [10], Data efficient image Transformers (DeiT) [64], Swin transformers (Swin) [23], and DeiT3 [65]. Depending on the number of parameters, transformers come in different sizes: Tiny (ViT-T), Small (ViT-S), Medium (DeiT3-M), Base (ViT-B), and Large (ViT-L).

We converted the weights of ViTs with absolute min-max quantization to INT8. Additionally, for static quantization, we calibrated the activations with a running histogram. During inference, the activations were quantized to UINT8. Input and output layers were also quantized. In our setup, we considered scalar quantization, i.e., we had a single FP scaling value for each quantized tensor eq. (1). We started from the same baseline static and dynamic quantized model for each run. Based on statically and dynamically quantized models, we compared them to the baseline using the HQ1, HQ2, and HQ3 algorithms. We computed the SQNR using 2000 samples and calibrated the proposed model by the algorithm with another 2000 samples. Both sets were randomly sampled from the ImageNet1K training set. This procedure was repeated five times to compute the mean and standard deviation of the accuracy, latency, and fraction of linear layers dynamically quantized. The accuracy was calculated over the ImageNet1K [9] validation set. We provided the mean and standard deviation of accuracy computed over 5 runs in the supplementary materials as well as the full results table.

We calculated the latency of linear layers statically and dynamically quantized with HQ1, HQ2, and HQ3 algorithms. For the experimental hardware, we selected the iPhone 13 Pro smartphone with an A15 Bionic CPU and GPU-accelerated NVIDIA A100 80GB GPU. We used PyTorch Mobile [60] with the QNNPACK [10] to measure smartphone latency. For the GPU-accelerated environment, we implemented quantized kernels using Triton [63]. In the supplementary material, we also provided an experimental evaluation for a CPU-only Intel Xeon 5218 Gold CPU using PyTorch with the FBGEMM [16]. Finally, for comparison, we reproduced the results of FQ-ViT and extended them to ViTs, DeiT, and DeiT3.

5 Analysis

Table 1 shows that ViT models are highly sensitive to quantization, which cause a significant drop in accuracy. We found that the FQ-ViT method was generally more effective than our HQ, except for ViT-B, with a patch size of 32. The use of dynamic quantization for linear layers in HQ2 did not improve performance for most models. However, HQ1 and HQ3 produced higher accuracy and lower latency for ViT-B/32 and ViT-L/32, where up to 50% of the linear layers were selected for dynamic quantization compared to static quantization. This resulted in an average speedup of 1.96 for ViT-B/32/224 with HQ1 and 1.58 for ViT-L/32/224 with HQ3 compared to dynamic quantization, as shown in Figure 2. Moreover, in the appendix, we presented the latency vs accuracy trade-off for the ViT-S/32/384. With the HQ1 and HQ3 algorithms we achieved, on average, a speedup of 1.92 and 1.62 times compared to dynamic quantization; see Table 2. At the same time, compared to static quantization, we improved accuracy by 12.07% and 11.48% for HQ1 and HQ3. Finally, for ViT models, our HQ1 and HQ3 methods reduced the latencies both on the A100 GPU and A15 CPU as shown in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Table 2 with respect to dynamic quantization.

Interestingly, statically quantized distilled DeiT models achieved higher or equal ac-

Figure 2: Average inference latency of models on A100 GPU. Each point represents a single quantization configuration.

Model	FP32	INT8	INT8-D	HQ1	HQ2	HQ3	FQ-ViT
ViT-S/16/224	81.39	77.01	79.34	77.12	73.43	77.05	78.58
ViT-S/32/224	75.99	45.59	74.38	60.93	59.43	60.58	59.13
ViT-B/16/224	85.10	73.15	84.15	71.76	70.27	74.89	83.70
ViT-B/32/224	80.71	71.35	79.13	75.10	74.99	74.57	70.99
ViT-B/32/384	83.35	81.32	82.70	81.44	80.49	81.16	81.37
ViT-L/16/224	85.85	84.30	85.48	83.94	84.18	84.40	84.97
DeiT-T/16/224*	74.50	74.16	74.06	74.03	73.31	73.94	73.63
DeiT-S/16/224*	81.22	80.75	80.79	80.86	80.66	80.68	80.42
DeiT-B/16/224*	83.39	82.92	82.48	82.87	82.96	82.51	82.48
DeiT3-S/16/224	81.37	78.95	80.63	79.42	78.93	79.26	79.62
DeiT3-M/16/224	83.09	79.47	82.74	79.72	79.59	79.56	82.1
DeiT3-B/16/224	83.79	76.54	83.51	80.81	80.40	80.15	0.10
DeiT3-B/16/384	85.07	80.98	84.79	82.19	82.99	81.99	0.10
DeiT3-L/16/224	84.78	71.77	84.61	83.27	82.01	80.29	0.10
Swin-S/4/224	83.30	82.70	83.26	82.69	82.74	82.69	82.40
Swin-B/4/224	85.27	84.19	84.99	84.16	84.21	84.18	82.50
Swin-L/4/224	86.32	85.72	86.28	85.77	85.78	85.75	85.61

Table 1: Comparison between baseline (FP32), static (INT8), dynamic (INT8-D), HQ1, HQ2, HQ3, and FQ-ViT. We report top-1 accuracy on the ImageNet1K dataset. In this table we present the best model out of 5 runs. The superscript ((*)) in DeiT denotes the distilled version. In bold we mark the best result between HQ and FQ-ViT.

accuracy to dynamic quantization, leaving little room for improvement. Nevertheless, our method improved the accuracy compared to the FQ-ViT method (Table 1) and decreased the latency compared to dynamic quantization for DeiT models; see Figure 3. For distilled DeiT-S/16/224 and DeiT-B/16/224, we reduced the latency by a factor of up to 2.51 and 2.15 with HQ1 algorithm; see Figure 2 and Table 2.

Figure 3: Average inference latency of models on A15 Bionic CPU. Each point represents a single quantization configuration.

Furthermore, our HQ methods achieved the highest improvements in accuracy in the most recent DeiT3 architecture. FQ-ViT applied to this architecture significantly affected the accuracy of the base and large models. In comparison, our method improved the accuracy by 4%, 2%, and 11.5% for DeiT3-B/16/224, DeiT3-B/16/384, and DeiT3-L/16/224, respectively; see Table 1. Moreover, we observed latency average speedups up to 1.80, 1.88, and 1.69 for the GPU (Figure 2), while for the A15 CPU, they were up to 1.27, 1.5, and 1.16 (Figure 3). Similarly to ViT models, the HQ2 algorithm selected on average 90% of dynamically quantized linear layers, while HQ1 and HQ3 selected, on average, up to 54% of dynamic layers. While those models were susceptible to high accuracy variance when statically quantized, DeiT3-L/16/224 models produced by HQ1 and HQ3 improved accuracy and latency as shown in the Table 2.

The difference in accuracy between dynamic and static quantization for Swin was less than 1%. Similarly to DeiT models, this family showed more robustness to quantization than ViT. Unfortunately, FQ-ViT did not improve the accuracy for Swin-S/4/224 over static quantization. All HQ algorithms favor static quantization over dynamic linear layers for Swin. However, the performance improvement over static quantization could be more robust.

6 Discussion

In our study, we addressed the challenge of quantizing ViTs. We observed that DeiT and Swin Transformer were more robust to static quantization than ViT and DeiT3. In particular, we found ViT volatile to static quantization, where the accuracy of tiny models dropped significantly. Nevertheless, our hybrid quantization algorithms improved in 12/12 ViT, 3/6 DeiT, 6/6 DeiT3, and 4/4 Swin Transformer models regarding accuracy and latency compared to static and dynamic quantization. Interestingly, Swin Transformers showed the most robust accuracy when statically compressed, and our HQ algorithms conservatively selected static quantization. For ViT and DeiT3, the HQ1 and HQ3 algorithms selected, on average,

Model	A15 CPU			A100 GPU		
	HQ1	HQ2	HQ3	HQ1	HQ2	HQ3
ViT-S/16/224	1.23	1.00	1.21	1.84	1.00	1.70
ViT-S/32/384	1.21	1.00	1.16	1.92	1.00	1.62
ViT-B/16/384	1.18	1.00	1.51	1.23	1.00	1.65
ViT-B/32/384	1.22	1.02	1.18	1.99	1.05	1.74
ViT-L/16/224	1.16	1.01	1.22	1.41	1.02	1.64
ViT - Avg. all	1.23	1.01	1.28	1.68	1.04	1.68
DeiT-T/16/224*	1.25	1.00	1.23	2.16	1.01	1.73
DeiT-S/16/224*	1.43	1.61	1.25	2.51	1.22	1.66
DeiT-B/16/224*	1.44	1.01	1.24	2.15	4.3	1.65
DeiT - Avg. all	1.29	1.15	1.21	2.02	1.67	1.66
DeiT3-S/16/224	1.22	1.01	1.22	1.81	1.00	1.87
DeiT3-B/16/224	1.17	1.00	1.27	1.47	1.00	1.80
DeiT3-B/16/384	1.50	1.01	1.42	1.88	1.00	1.57
DeiT3-L/16/224	1.16	1.00	1.15	1.69	1.00	1.49
DeiT3 - Avg. all	1.33	1.01	1.29	1.72	1.01	1.69

Table 2: Average speedup latency improvement over five runs of hybrid quantization compared to dynamic quantization for representative models of ViT families for an A15 CPU and an NVIDIA A100 GPU. In bold, we mark the best latency speedup for each environment.

up to 62% and 54% of dynamic layers. The FQ-ViT algorithm improved the accuracy of the ViT model. However, the model performance dropped significantly for a newer architecture such as DeiT3. The authors of FQ-ViT did not provide latency measurements, and we could not measure the speedups as the released code simulates the quantization of their method. Since FQ-ViT proposed integer approximations of the LayerNorm and Softmax activation functions, it could be combined with our method to improve accuracy,

We have shown that hybrid quantization could consistently improve latency and accuracy across the experimental setup. Moreover, we have used PyTorch on mobile and data center workstations, showing the capability to deploy the models on those platforms. Our intuition regarding hybrid quantization was verified for HQ1 and HQ3, where we improved the accuracy and latency measurements of quantized models on the A15 CPU and A100 GPU over static and dynamic quantization. DeiT3 base models achieved up to 1.88 and 1.50 latency speedup compared to dynamic quantization on A100 GPU and A15 CPU, with up to 4% improvement in accuracy. Similarly, for the DeiT3-L model, we improved the accuracy by up to 11.5% and the average speedup by up to 1.69 on the A100 GPU and 1.16 on the A15 CPU.

In our study, we focused on quantization with scalar scaling factors and HQ schemes. Moreover, the performance of the model after HQ quantization depended on the baseline of the statically quantized model. Also, the choice of layers depended on the stochasticity of the samples selected for comparison. Furthermore, our method kept the skip connection in FP arithmetic to let the signal flow through the network to dynamically quantized layers.

Our research has shown that combining static and dynamic quantization can improve the performance of ViTs. On the one hand, we found that the HQ1 and HQ3 algorithms adequately balanced the static-to-dynamic linear ratio and would be preferable to HQ2, which

mostly selected dynamic quantization. On the other hand, we note that the HQ2 algorithm includes quantized normalization, activation, and attention. We expect the models quantized with HQ2 to require less memory than with dynamic quantization. Moreover, in our study, we found that HQ1 consequently provided better top-1 accuracy on the ImageNet1K validation dataset and improved latency over HQ3. However, it would be beneficial in future studies to extend the algorithm with a mixed-precision linear layer. This would further reduce the memory requirements. In addition, selecting a quantization method other than scalar quantization for static model baselines could improve the model performance produced by the HQ algorithms.

7 Conclusions

We have introduced three new HQ algorithms. Our algorithms use the SQNR metric to select dynamic over static linear layers for quantization. Adding dynamic quantization to the model may seem like a disadvantage from the latency vs. accuracy point of view, but our method improved accuracy and reduced the latency of the ViT and DeiT3 models. Specifically, our method improved the accuracy by 1%, 4%, 2%, and 11.5% on the classification task over static quantization for DeiT3-S/16/224, DeiT3-B/16/224, DeiT3-B/16/384, and DeiT3-L/16/224, respectively. Furthermore, we showed that we reduced the inference latency on mobile A15 CPU and A100 GPU compared to dynamic quantization. For those models, we achieved speedup averages of 1.81, 1.47, 1.88, and 1.69 for the HQ1 algorithm and 1.87, 1.80, 1.57, and 1.49 for the HQ3 algorithm compared to dynamic quantization on NVIDIA A100 GPU.

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